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Properties of interfacial layer in surfactant-laden concentrate titania nanoparticle dispersions

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In the context of the fabrication of porous material, more specifically solid foams, from particle-stabilized liquid foams, the understanding of the physicochemical parameters and phenomena controlling the interface adsorption of these particles in the lamella is essential. In many cases, particle-based foam stabilization is obtained by adding a surfactant to a dispersion, to render the particles partially hydrophobic. This facilitates the migration towards the interface of the surfactant-coated particles, forming a viscoelastic layer.

In this work, the properties of the interfacial layer of TiO₂ concentrate (up to 5% wt) nanoparticle (NP) dispersions containing cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) are addressed. More specifically, both the effect of the concentration of CTAB, adsorbed on the NPs, and the concentration of coated NPs in the dispersion are analysed.

The properties of the interfacial layer are measured by the Pendant Drop technique. The experiments were performed at 20°C in a temperature-controlled cuvette. In addition to dynamic surface tension, dilatational rheology was investigated at different frequencies, obtaining the values for surface elasticity and viscosity. After the spontaneous formation of an interfacial layer, an increase of the adsorption rate was observed, during the imposed drop area oscillation. This phenomenon depends on the CTAB concentration and seems to be related to a particle rearrangement in the adsorption layer induced by the area perturbation. In addition, an evident minimum in the modulus of the dilatational viscoelasticity is observed as a function of the concentration of coated NPs, that could also be related to rearrangements in the layer.

Keywords: TiO₂ dispersion, surface rheology, CTAB, water-air interface

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Figure 1. Effect of particle adsorption on the measured surface tension (left), on the measured viscoelasticity (center) and schematic of the migration of CTAB-coated particles to the interface.

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References

- [1] S. Llamas, et al., 2019 Colloids and Surfaces A, 575, 299-309.
- [2] A. Maestro et al., 2015 Advances in Condensed Matter Physics, 917516.
- [3] D. Zabiegaj, et al. 2015 Colloids and Surfaces A, 473, 24-31.

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Materials

- **TiO₂ nanoparticles (NP):** Dispersions of Evonik VP Disp. W 2730 X
 - BET Specific surface area (m²/g) = 96.5
 - NP density (g/cm³) = 3.88
 - NP Radius by BET (R_{BET}) (nm) = 8.0
 - NP Radius by DLS (R_h) (nm) = 19.1
 - ζ-potential (mV) = -46.3
 - Dispersion density (g/cm³) = 1.28
 - pH value = 6 - 8
 - Dispersions dilutions 0.5 – 7.5 %wt
- Addition of **cationic surfactant, CTAB**, to create partially hydrophobic NP-surfactant complexes.
 - Range of CTAB solutions: 1E-7 to 1E-2 M
- From previous studies, within the studied NP and CTAB range, all surfactant is adsorbed at the NP surface.
- Under these conditions, increasing the CTAB concentration increases the NP hydrophobicity and facilitates the migration towards the water/air interface forming a NP viscoelastic layer.

Methods

The interfacial properties of dispersions formed by TiO₂ nanoparticles at concentration up to 7.5 wt%, and CTAB at different concentrations are studied.

- Measurements performed with dynamic Pendant Drop apparatus (PAT1, Sinterface)
- Dilational Rheology by the Oscillating Drop methodology at frequencies between 0.005 to 0.3 Hz.
- Temperature 20 °C

Dependence of surfactant coverage of nanoparticles (constant NP concentration and variable CTAB concentration)

Adsorption of surfactant-NP complexes at liquid-air interface

Dependence of NP-surfactant complexes concentration (constant surfactant adsorption on particles $\Gamma=0.0002\text{mol/m}^2$)

Fig. 1 : Equilibrium surface tension vs. CTAB adsorbed on TiO₂ NP, after the spontaneous formation of the adsorption layer (top) and corresponding modulus of the dilational viscoelasticity at 0.02Hz (bottom).

Fig. 2: Equilibrium surface tension (ST) vs. NP concentration at fixed surfactant coverage, after the spontaneous adsorption (top) and modulus of the dilational viscoelasticity for various perturbation periods (bottom).

Dilational rheology during layer formation

Fig. 3: Modulus of the dilational viscoelasticity during the formation of the surface layer obtained by the induced oscillating surface tension during adsorption (see insert).

Conclusions

- The NP-surfactant complexes adsorb at the liquid interface provided they are sufficiently hydrophobic.
- In that case, the complexes behave as regular surfactants: the ST decreases with increasing the complexes concentration.
- Dilational rheology presents instead a complex behavior, with an evident minimum at intermediate concentration of the complexes.
- After the spontaneous formation of an interfacial layer, an increase of the adsorption rate was observed, during the imposed drop area oscillation.
- At the first stage of the formation of the adsorption layer, an evident minimum in the modulus of the dilational viscoelasticity is observed.
- These phenomena could be related to rearrangement of the complexes in the adsorption layer induced by the area perturbation and/or to the partially irreversible complex adsorption.
- This study is inserted in a wider project for the synthesis of solid foams with catalytic properties.

References

[1] S. Llamas, et al., 2019 Colloids and Surfaces A, 575, 299-309. [2] A. Maestro et al., 2015 Advances in Condensed Matter Physics, 917516. [3] D. Zabiegaj, et al. 2015 Colloids and Surfaces A, 473, 24-31.

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